

Herbo-mineral and biological resources used for fumigation therapy in siddha medicine: Systematic review

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Abstract

Fumigation therapy is a one of the types of treatment in Siddha medicine, which using medicinal smoke for cure and prevent the diseases. It has been used for decontamination of the environment, infected area and also treating diseases like arthritis, sinusitis, terminal stage of piles and respiratory disorders. However, extensive use and scientific validation of fumigation remains limited. The highlights of this review are focused on the Herbal, Metal, Mineral and Biological resources on fumigation therapy with scientific validation that are extensively employed as a medicinal raw material in Siddha Medicine

A systematic review was conducted following PRISMA guidelines and which incorporates studies from Scopus, Web of Science, PubMed and reputed Siddha journals. Clinical and preclinical studies, case reports and original Siddha texts were consulted to establish the pharmacological significance of fumigation therapy.

The presence of significant bioactive compounds, such as volatile oils, chavicine, α -pinene, β -sitosterol, flavonoids, terpenoids, thymol, terpenes, phenolic compounds like γ -terpinene, polypeptides, proteins, muscone, musclide, steroids like muscopyridine and cyclohexadecanone, shows the significant therapeutic potential these components hold. These bioactive compounds exhibit diverse pharmacological activities that are beneficial for treating a wide range of disease conditions, including antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and detoxifying properties. These actions show very good effect in infections control, reducing inflammation, enhance the healing of chronic wounds and subside the respiratory diseases.

In addition to these therapeutic properties, fumigation therapy has been exhibited for its positive impact on mental well-being and public health. Fumigation helps to reduce environmental decontamination, which not only use in maintaining hygiene but also has a preventive and curative role in healthcare. It is useful for promoting health by reducing microbial activity and improving quality of air, which is essential in areas with high disease burden.

This systematic review concludes that fumigation therapy significantly enhances promotion of health, prevention and cure of disease. Integrating scientific validation with siddha concepts gives an opportunity to improve evidence-based medical practices and interventions and contributing to better public health outcomes.

Keywords: Scientific Validation; Preventive; Fumigation Therapy; Health; Curative.

1. Introduction

Infectious diseases may spread from an individual to another person or any other mode of transmission to person. Most of the contagious diseases are airborne which spread by tiny pathogens like bacteria, fungi and viruses in the air. These

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diseases are mostly spread by sneezing, coughing with phlegm. Airborne diseases are the most widespread, and complete prevention is complicated. [1] These pandemic conditions had occurred in ancient times. These may occur as pandemic conditions some time in ancient times even recent past we all had experience COVID-19 viral infections. [2] Antimicrobial properties of medicinal fumes gained attention for reducing viral transmission. At that time, "Pugai" (Fumigation therapy) had been mentioned for treating these types of airborne diseases spread by air. The "Pugai" is very easy to administer through nose, It is the best route for fumigation therapy for airborne diseases. "Sungan" a traditional inhalation apparatus which facilitates the admiration of medicinal fumes through the nose or mouth and expose to the affected area. [3]

It is a method by which drugs of herbo-mineral or biological origin are used for fumigation "Pugai" (Fumigation therapy) is one of the measures suggested for the maintenance of the internal and external environment of an Individuals. [4] Because this have been used as a disinfectant for medicinal fumigation therapy and also it can fumigate the environment also. "Pugai" widely used in Siddha Pharmaceutical Preparation for various reasons such as: Sterilizing the pots in which medicines have to be stored, Purification and sanitization or fumigation of premises, repelling the insects and poisonous animals, treating infectious and contagious diseases. [5] It has been helping to reduce mental stress and enhance mood. This procedure deeply interconnected with the cultural and spiritual way of Siddha medicine, which make attention of holistic approach to healing. [6]

Fumigation therapy gives a special fusion of siddha knowledge with a modern antimicrobial action, with its various applications from physical cure to environmental decontaminations. The growing challenges showed by the drug resistance of organisms and viral pandemics underline the importance of alternative therapy. While many siddha remedies have been listed in siddha text, scientific evaluate documentation remains limited. With increasing global identity of Siddha medicine, it is important to explore and validate the pharmacological actions of fumigation therapy. This review connects the gap between the siddha medical knowledge and scientific evidence by systematic analysis the potential of herbs, minerals and biological resources used in siddha fumigation therapy. Siddha fumigation therapy, which combining herbs, minerals and biological resources, is hypothesized to exhibit antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and healing properties, that providing diverse therapeutic benefits. This study aims to elicit the potency of herbs, minerals and biological resources for the fumigation therapy.

2. Methodology

This systemic review was conducted according to the PRISMA guidelines to make sure methodological stability, transparency and standard. A comprehensive search of e-database such as Scopus, Web of Science PubMed and Google Scholar were searched out to find relevant studies. In addition, primary Siddha texts, including *Gunapadam Thathu Jeeva Vakuppu*, Tamil English Dictionary of Medicine, Chemistry, Botany and Allied Sciences (Based on Indian Medical Science), and *Siddha Maruthuvam Sirappu*, were thoroughly analyzed to extract siddha medical insights and documented evidence related to fumigation practices and their therapeutic significance. Bibliographies of selected studies were manually screened to identify additional sources, ensuring comprehensive coverage of the topic.

The review included studies focusing on fumigation therapy in Siddha medicine, emphasizing the use of herbs, minerals and biological resources and their chemical compositions and pharmacological properties for the diseases. Clinical and preclinical studies, reviews, case reports, and ancient Siddha manuscripts written in English were included. Exclusion criteria were studies unrelated to Siddha fumigation therapy, articles lacking full text availability, and non-peer reviewed sources.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Procedures regarding Siddha Fumigation Therapy

Fumigation therapy is a milestone of Siddha medicine, which consist a various preparation and administration process involving specific tools and patient-oriented protocols. Important equipment required for the preparation process of fumigation drugs includes a stone and steel mortar and pestle, a crushing steel mortar and rod, *kalkam* (grinding stone), a stove, spoons, an oven and oil lamps. To make sure the effective administration, private rooms for male and female patients are arranged and sterile gloves, gauze, cotton, spirit and oils such as castor and gingelly oil are used. [3,4,5]

This fumigation process involves grinding the relevant herbs into paste or powder using iron mortar and pestle. The herbal paste is wrapped in clean cloth, rolled into sticks and then ignited to release fumes; which are exposed to the specific area of administration. [2] Alternatively, herbal powder can be filled in *Sungan* and burned at one end, which

allowing the fumes to be inhaled through the nostrils or mouth, depending on the condition. In some cases, tamarind twigs are combined with ingredients of herbal powder, placed on burning charcoal and the resulting fumes are directed towards the affected site.^[3]

Patients, those who are willing to get fumigation are carefully prepared before treatment. They are instructed to drink plenty of water to avoid dehydration caused by thermal exposure. Privacy is ensured by covering areas other than the site of administration. The site is cleaned thoroughly with purified water before the procedure. The inhalation process, which facilitated by the *Sungan* pipe, which is designed to treat respiratory issues with specific guidance provided to avoid complications. For disorders involving nasal pathways, all the patients inhale the smoke through their nostrils and exhale through the mouth to prevent heat related problems.^[5]

Other administration methods including fumigation direct toward specific skin manifestations, wounds or ulcers. For anorectal or vaginal conditions, patients are seated on a specialized stool with an opening that allows exposure to the medicinal fumes.^[6] Each session typically lasts for 10-15 minutes and is conducted daily for a week. During the treatment period; patients are advised to avoid food before the procedure but are encouraged to drink water. Post-treatment plan for patients that are instructed to eat milk rice and avoid sour, salty or spicy foods to enhance the therapy efficacy of therapy.^[4,5]

Fumigation therapy is contraindicated for certain populations that including infants, pregnant and lactating women, alcoholics, anemic patients and those with bleeding disorders or gonorrhoea. This precautionary approach emphasizes the personalized and patient-centered nature of Siddha medicine.^[2,3]

3.2. Therapeutic Role of Herbs, Minerals and Biological Resources

3.2.1. Herbal Plants

Herbal plants are very significant to Siddha fumigation therapy, because which offering a wide range of therapeutic benefits. The reputed siddha pharmacology text, which mentioned that the fumes of plants such as Seed of *Kothamalli* (*Coriandrum sativum* L.) and *Eluppai* (*Madhuca longifolia* (L.) J.F.Macbr.); leaves of *Oomathai* (*Datura metel* L.), *Mul Murukku* (*Erythrina variegata* var. *alba*), *Nochi* (*Vitex negundo* L.) and *Thumbai* (*Leucas aspera* (Willd.) Link.); bark of *Agil* (*Aquilaria agallocha* Roxb.) and *Puliyampattai* (*Tamarindus indica* L.); tuber of *Kottam* (*Costus speciosus* (J.Koenig) Sm.) and *Visha Mungil* (*Crinum asiaticum* L.); whole plant of *Brahmathandu* (*Argemone mexicana* L.) effectively cures the diseases such as microbial infections, eczema, asthma, eye diseases, sinusitis, insect bites, relieving nausea decomposed ulcers, Insomnia, Chronic wounds and dental issues like toothaches respectively.^[7] These plants mainly contain chemical composition such as linalool, saponins, scopolamine, hyoscyamine, flavonoids, terpenoids, diosgenin, lycorine and sanguinarine; mainly act as an anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic and bronchodilators.^[8]

Seeds of *Milagu* (*Piper nigrum* L.) contains piperine, volatile oils, chavicine, flavonoids and phenolic components, which exhibit antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant properties, that fume make it effective in relieving colds, cough, rhinitis and respiratory issues while against microbial infections.^[9] Rhizome of *Sukku* (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe.) is rich in gingerol, shogaol and phenolic compounds, which provide anti-inflammatory, mucolytic and stimulant action, so it fumes relieves sinusitis, respiratory congestion and nausea.^[10]

Rhizome of *Manjal* (*Curcuma longa* L.), with curcumin and turmerone, offers antiseptic and immune boosting properties and fumigation of *manjal* helps in the treatment of respiratory ailments and wound healing.^[11]

Seed of *Kandankathari* (*Solanum surattense* Burm.f.) consist of solanine and solasodine, which act as bronchodilators and antimicrobial, that fume help to treat asthma, bronchitis and also reduce toothache and expel the worms from teeth.^[12] Bark of *Santhanam* (*Santalum album* L.) contains santalol and terpenoids, which provide antiseptic, analgesic and cooling effects, so that fume relieves headaches, fevers and skin issues.^[13] Flower of *Erukku* (*Calotropis gigantea* (L.)) contains calotropin and glycosides, which providing anti-inflammatory and antibacterial effects that fume relieve chronic ulcers, asthma and eczema.^[14]

Leaves and bark of *Maa* (*Mangifera indica* L.) have mangiferin and tannins, exhibits antimicrobial and antioxidant properties, fume that treating tonsillitis, hiccups and fungal infections while repelling mosquitoes.^[15] Seed of *Sathakuppai* (*Anethum graveolens* L.), rich in scopoletin and flavonoids, acts as anti-inflammatory; That fumigation relieves respiratory disorders.^[16] Leaves of *Thulasi* (*Ocimum sanctum* Linn.) that contain *Ocimum* and phenol which act as an antioxidant, antibacterial and antifungal, so fume heal the wound effectively.^[17]

Barks of *Vembu Pattai* (*Azadirachta indica* Adr. Juss.), containing azadirachtin, which has antibacterial and antiviral properties, fume that treating chickenpox, wounds and insect infestations. [18] Resin of *Sambirani* (*Styrax benzoin* Dryand.) provides aromatic, antimicrobial and its fume repels the insects, sterilizing room and reducing chronic coughs. [19] Seed of *Thippili* (*Piper longum* L.), with piperine and thymol, act as bronchodilator and mucolytic action, fume that relieves rhinitis and improves respiratory function. [20] Leaves of *Adathodai* (*Justicia adhatoda* L.), containing vasicine, which is potent expectorant and its fume effective in treating asthma and clearing respiratory passages. [21] Seed of *Karambu* (*Syzygium aromaticum* (L.) Merr.), which contains sesquiterpenes and eugenol, which are act as antiseptic, anti-inflammatory, antifungal and anti-bacterial, so fume of *karambu* cures dental carries, toothache and chronic wounds. [22]

Resin of *Parangi Sambrani* (*Boswellia glabra* Roxb.), with boswellic acid, which is a bronchodilator, fume that cleanses the air and treats respiratory conditions. [23] Root of *Ven Kodi Veli* (*Plumbago zeylanica* L.) and *Seng Kodi Veli* (*Plumbago rosea* L.), containing plumbagin and chitanone respectively, both acts as anti-bacterial, anti-fungal and antiseptic, so their fume eliminates fungal growth, heals chronic wounds and infections. [24] Leaves of *Thalisapathiri* (*Cinnamomum tamala* (Buch. Ham.)), containing and eugenol, which have anti-inflammatory action and that fume treats sinusitis and headaches. [25] Seed of *Karuncheeragam* (*Nigella sativa* L.) that contains nigellicine, nigellimine and dithymoquinone and those are act as bronchodilator, anti-microbial and anti-inflammatory, fume useful to treat respiratory disorder. [26]

Rhizome of *Vasambu* (*Acorus calamus* L.), which has glycosides and flavonoids, act as insecticidal and sedative; that fume eliminates pests and relieves anxiety. [27] Bulb of *Vellulli* (*Allium sativum* L.), that contains alliin and allacin, which act as anti-bacterial and antiseptic, that treats respiratory infections and repels pests. [28] Bark of *Devadaru* (*Cedrus deodara*. (Roxb.)) has β sitosterol, that provides anti-inflammatory effects and fume treats respiratory issues. [29] Leaves of *Kuppai meni* (*Acalypha indica* L.), rich in alkaloids, and act as antimicrobial, that fume treats wounds and eliminates pests. [30] Seed of *Cheek kai* (*Acacia sinuata* (Lour.) Merr.), containing phenols; that fume, which treats infections and enhances air quality. [31] Resin of *Kungiliyam* (*Shorea robusta* C.F.Gaertn) has tannins that shows anti-fungal and antiseptic actions, so that fume heals wounds and infections. [32]

3.2.2. Minerals in Fumigation Therapy

After the purification process of minerals which are compatible and palatable to use as internal medicine. So, they can be safely used in a fumigation process. [33] Purified *Karuvangam* (Plumbum) has antiseptic and astringent properties, fume which is highly effective in treating venereal ulcers and the action of *karuvangam*, which disinfects the affected areas, providing relief from infections and enhance the wound healing. [33, 34] Similarly; Purified *Rasam* (Mercury) is very potent for its anti-inflammatory properties and traditionally employed in fumigation therapy to cure *vatha*-related diseases such as rheumatism and pricking pain. In addition to its anti-inflammatory effects, *Rasam* demonstrates antimicrobial and detoxifying actions; making it highly beneficial for purifying the air and treat chronic inflammatory conditions through fumigation. [33, 35]

Purified *Thalagam* (Yellow Arsenic Tri Sulfide) exhibits potent anti-microbial and anti-inflammatory effects. The fumes with this compound are particularly effective for managing deep wounds and foul-smelling ulcers by disinfecting and reducing inflammation in the affected areas. [33, 36] Similarly; Purified *Lingam* (Red Sulphide of Mercury), shows anti-inflammatory, analgesic and antimicrobial properties. It is very effective for deep wounds and foul-smelling ulcers by promoting healing and reducing microbial infections in fumigation. [33, 37] Purified *Chunnambu* (Calcium carbonate) contains phenolic compounds, which are flavonoids such as hesperidin and limocitrin and phenolic acids such as ferulic and p-hydroxybenzoic acids along with monoterpenoids like D-limonene, β -pinene and γ -terpinene. These compounds exhibit anxiolytic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant properties. These fumes beneficial for fumigation to address conditions like sinus infections, respiratory inflammation and infectious skin diseases. [33, 38]

Purified *Gandhagam* (Sulfur) indicates antiseptic and insecticidal properties and its fumes are particularly useful in venereal diseases, dermatological conditions, anorectal diseases, ulcers and swellings. Sulfur fumigation is a Siddha remedy for treating chronic and infectious conditions. [33, 39] Likewise, Purified *Gowri* (Arsenic Penta Sulfide) demonstrates antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties. Its smoke is traditionally used to treat delirium, scabies, poisonous bites and hemorrhagic conditions and also disinfecting and soothing the affected areas. [33, 40]

Purified *Veeram* (Hydrargyrum Perchloride) possesses antiseptic and allergenic properties. The fumes from *Veeram* are widely recognized for treating leprosy, morbid growths of flesh, venereal diseases and piles, as well as for disinfecting chronic wounds and skin infections. [33, 41] Similarly; Purified *Vellai Paadaanam* (White Arsenic/Arsenious Acid) acts as an antibacterial and antipyretic agent. These Chemical properties are particularly effective for treating skin

diseases, wounds and syphilis; which are enhancing wound healing and providing cure from chronic infections in fumigation. [33, 41]

Purified *Manosilai* (Bisulphuret of Arsenic) is traditionally used in fumigation therapy for its effective treatment for vitiligo. The fumes promote healing and pigmentation restoration in affected skin areas. [33]

Purified *Navacharam* (Ammonium Chloride) exhibits expectorant, diaphoretic and stimulant actions. Its fumes are effective for conditions such as headaches, rhinitis, syncope with pain and cold body and as well as scabies, eczema, herpes zoster and Hansen's disease. This therapy helps to relieve congestion and disinfect the skin lesions. [33, 42] Purified *Ambar* (Ambra Grasea) acts as a stimulant and its fumes are particularly beneficial for subside migraines by providing soothing and calming effects on the nervous system. [33] Lastly, Purified *Thrusu* (Copper Sulphate) exhibits astringent, antiseptic, stimulant, styptic and mild caustic properties. Fumigation with *Thrusu* is effective in controlling nose bleeding, disinfecting wounds and managing inflammatory conditions, making it an essential resource in fumigation applications. [33, 43]

3.2.3. Biological Resources in Fumigation Therapy

Animal derivatives offer unique therapeutic properties. *Kadal Nurai* (Sea Foam) comprises of magnesium, strontium, iron, trace amounts of copper and zinc, aragonite and β -chitin; which exhibit healing and restorative components. In the fumigation therapy, it shows therapeutic effects by facilitating in the healing of wounds and chronic ulcers through its anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activity. [33, 44] *Pavazham* (Coral) consists of sodium, iron, calcium, phosphorus, sulfur and magnesium, which elicit antimicrobial, hemostatic and astringent properties. Its fumigation uses to reduce excessive phlegm, controls cough and venereal diseases through its disinfecting and drying effects. [33, 45]

Muthu (Pearl), composed of conchiolin, orthorhombic acid and calcium carbonate, which exhibits mucolytic and properties of enhance respiratory and that fume provides therapeutic effects by relieving respiratory disorders, clearing mucus and improving airflow during congestion. [33, 46] Similarly, *Kasthoori* (Musk from *Moschus moschiferous*) contains polypeptides, proteins, muscone, musclide, steroids and muscopyridine, which exhibit anti-inflammatory and hyperthermic properties. Its smoke exerts its therapeutic effects by treating delirium, asthma and epilepsy conditions, helping to calm the nervous system and open respiratory passages. [33, 47] Additionally, *Punugu* (Civet) contains cyclopentadecanone, cyclohexadecanone, cycloheptadecanone and 6-cis-cycloheptadecenone, which exhibit mucolytic and properties which are soothing the respiratory. Its fume particularly effective in loosening thickened mucus and controlling intractable cough in conditions like whooping cough; especially in children. [33, 48]

In concern to the fumigation therapy, the challenges while increased levels of particulate air pollution are associated with increased respiratory and cardiovascular system but Ultrafine particles (UFP; less than 0.1 micro meter in aerodynamic diameter) may contribute to the health effects of particulate matter (PM) for a number of reasons.[49]

4. Conclusion

This systematic review concludes that fumigation therapy act as a powerful sterilization technique, decontaminating surroundings and preventing the spread of infections. Utilization of diverse herbs, purified minerals and biological resources rich in pharmacological actions and phytochemical constituents causes very effective approach to health. Hence, significantly enhances promotion of health, prevention and cure of disease. Integrating scientific validation with siddha concepts gives an opportunity to improve evidence based medical practices and interventions and contributing to better public health outcomes.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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Appendix

Coriandrum sativum

Madhuca longifolia

Datura metel

Erythrina variegata

Vitex negundo

Leucas aspera

Aquilaria agallocha

Tamarindus indica

Costus speciosus

Crinum asiaticum

Argemone mexicana

Piper nigrum

Zingiber officinale

Curcuma longa

Solanum surattense

Santalum album

Calotropis gigantea

Mangifera indica

Anethum graveolens

Ocimum sanctum

Azadirachta indica

Styrax benzoin

Piper longum

Justicia adhatoda

Syzygium aromaticum

Boswellia glabra

Plumbago zeylanica

Plumbago rosea

Cinnamomum tamala

Nigella sativa

Acorus calamus

Allium sativum

Cedrus deodara

Acalypha indica

Acacia sinuata

Shorea robusta

Plumbum

Mercury

Yellow Arsenic Tri Sulfide

Red Sulphide of Mercury

Calcium carbonate

Sulfur

Arsenic Sulfide

Penta

Hydrargyrum Perchlorate

White Arsenic

Bisulphuret of Arsenic

Ammonium Chloride

Ambra Grasea

Copper Sulphate

Sea Foam

Coral

Pearl

Musk Moschus moschiferous

Civet